

ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC PRINCIPLES AND PATTERNS OF LAND USE BY DEHKAN AND HOUSEHOLD FARMS

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***Abstract.** Efficient use of land resources in dehkan and household farms is a key factor in ensuring food security and sustainable agricultural development under conditions of limited arable land. Due to natural and anthropogenic impacts, the quality and availability of agricultural land are gradually decreasing, which increases the importance of improving land use efficiency. This article analyzes the organizational and economic foundations of land use in dehkan and household farms, identifies existing problems in land accounting, financial support, and the application of modern agrotechnologies. Based on a sociological survey conducted in the Ishtikhan district of Samarkand region, the main factors affecting land use efficiency are assessed. The study highlights the importance of introducing geoinformation technologies, strengthening institutional mechanisms, and expanding support services to improve land productivity and farm incomes.*

***Key words.** land resources, dehkan farms, household plots, land use efficiency, organizational and economic mechanisms, agricultural land management, geoinformation technologies, food security, sustainable rural development.*

Introduction. The world land fund today is 13.4 billion hectares, of which only 1.5 billion hectares, or 11%, are economically advantageous for agricultural production. Their quantity and quality are decreasing year by year under the influence of natural and anthropogenic factors and processes. Along with the development of new lands for agricultural use, the deterioration of the melioration state of lands, erosion, drought, increasing salinity and the impact of groundwater, industrial and transport construction, and the open development of mineral resources are accelerating the withdrawal of agricultural land from circulation on a global scale. Therefore, the main problem of the world land fund is solving the global food problem and increasing the productivity and efficiency of land resources limited for use in agriculture.

Therefore, in the context of innovative reforms and modernization of the country's economy, supporting the use of land resources in dehkan and household farms and improving its mechanisms is becoming one of the most important priority tasks not only for the sustainable development of agriculture, the effective use of dehkan farms and household plots, but also for increasing the efficiency and competitiveness of agricultural production, ensuring food security and increasing the export potential of the republic.

The Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law “On Dehkan Farms” (2021), as well as a number of decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the government, in accordance with the priority tasks and measures defined, lay the foundation for a new stage in supporting the activities of dehkan and subsidiary farms on land use, and at the same time define new tasks in this area.

Problem statement. From this perspective, the consistent development of dehkan farms

and household plot owners' activities in our country is inextricably linked with supporting them and organizing the effective use of their potential. Currently, dehkan and household farms are also contributing to the development of various economic sectors. In this regard, it is crucial to properly allocate land to dehkan and household farms and organize the rational use of allocated land. Therefore, it is necessary to identify problems affecting the development of dehkan and household farms, make effective decisions to solve them, and determine appropriate measures. Today, a number of issues are observed in the effective organization of dehkan and household farms' activities, which are among the agricultural enterprises in the republic that meet the population's demand for agricultural products.

For instance, in our republic, due to improper accounting of existing dehkan and household farm lands and weak state and public control over their intended use, there are violations of legal requirements for managing dehkan and household farms. Additionally, these farms lack sufficient funds for the effective use of their lands, which is leading to the deterioration of these farmlands.

From this point of view, in order to effectively organize the activities of using the lands of dehkan and household plots, it is necessary to create opportunities for the use of modern technologies in the accounting of these lands. Especially today, a low level of accuracy in land accounting is observed in these farms. This requires increasing the accuracy and perfection of land accounting based on the use of modern geoinformation technologies and drones in practice. In addition, the lack of clear mechanisms for fulfilling the requirements of legislative acts adopted to support the activities of dehkan and household farms on the use of land negatively affects the development of dehkan and household farms. At the same time, we consider it expedient to introduce preferential mortgage loans in order to further strengthen the activities of dehkan and household plot farms.

In order to ensure high-quality delivery of agricultural products to markets and further increase the income of dehkan and household farms, it is necessary to pay special attention to expanding the activities of service industries in the districts. Moreover, if advanced agricultural technologies, such as greenhouses and drip irrigation methods, were used in the use of farms and household plots, the efficiency of land use would increase. It should be noted that the problems affecting the support of dehkan and household plots were studied in several regions of the republic. In particular, the results of a social survey conducted in the Ishtikhan district of the Samarkand region are presented in Table 1. Currently, the total land area of the district is 71,822 thousand hectares, of which 7,729 thousand hectares are allocated to dehkan and household farms, of which 6,119 thousand hectares are irrigated land.

Table 1. Results of a survey conducted among dehkan farms and owners of household plots in the Ishtikhan district of the Samarkand region (as of July-August 2025)

Number of dehkan and subsidiary farms surveyed - 35				
№	Questions	Respondents' answers		
		Answer options	Number	Percent
1.	What services do you need in your farm or household?	pedigree cattle, seedlings, seeds, transport, etc.	26	74
		no need for services	9	26
2.	Are you using advanced land use technologies in farming or household plots?	yes (greenhouse, drip irrigation of crops, etc.)	13	37
		no	22	63

3.	Do you know how to use websites, in particular tomorqa uz, as well as the website of the advisory centers of the Ministry of Agriculture, to manage your farm or household plot?	yes	8	23
		no	27	77

If we analyze the answers of the heads of dehkan farms and owners of household plots, for example, to the question "What services are needed in your farm?" 74 percent of respondents answered that they need such services as pedigree cattle, seedlings, seeds, and transport for the development of their farm. 63 percent stated that they do not use advanced technologies for land use (hot rooms, drip irrigation, intensive orchards, etc.) in farming or household plots. 77 percent of respondents said that they do not know how to use websites, in particular, tomorqa uz, as well as the website of advisory centers of the Ministry of Agriculture, to manage a dehkan or household plot. Thus, as can be seen from the answers to these questions, the organization of the activities of dehkan and household farms requires solving many problems. If we pay attention to the first question, providing them with various seedlings and seeds would create significant advantages for the development of these farms, and in turn, the use of advanced agricultural technologies in these farms will mobilize reserves for further increasing their capabilities and potential.

In general, if measures to support the activities of dehkan and household farms in the use of land, especially in irrigated regions of the country, are purposefully implemented based on the requirements of legislative acts, this will not only prevent the land of these farms from becoming unusable, but also ensure the continuity and effectiveness of the process of their reproduction.

From this perspective, several provisions of the Land Code require amendments. Specifically, the second part of Article 39 states, “A citizen who owns land may pledge the right of lifelong inheritable possession of a land plot, including such rights acquired through auction, to obtain loans for operating a dehkan farm or building individual housing”. However, this provision is not currently functional due to the lack of an organizational and economic mechanism for its implementation. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a mechanism to implement this provision in accordance with the current market economy and create a corresponding by-law document. This by-law document should establish procedures for evaluating ownership rights to dehkan and household plot lands or for privatizing these lands, as well as recognizing their value or privatization documents as collateral for obtaining bank loans. An exception should be made for the land on which a citizen's dwelling is located to prevent further exacerbation of housing problems in rural areas. In case of loan default, the bank may temporarily grant the land plot to a third party for use in accordance with paragraph 8 of part 1 of this article. A mechanism for implementing this provision also needs to be developed.

According to the fourth paragraph of the first part of Article 46 of the Land Code, land allocation is specified “for citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan - for dehkan farms, individual gardening, vegetable growing, and animal husbandry”. It is advisable to amend this provision to read “land allocation for citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan - for dehkan farms, individual gardening, viticulture, melon growing, mulberry cultivation, nursery farming, floriculture, animal husbandry, poultry farming, rabbit breeding, fish farming, beekeeping, fur farming, and other activities”. This is because during his visits to the regions, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan has provided numerous directives on diversifying land resource use. In this regard,

creating a specific system of land use requires, first and foremost, establishing its legal foundations and mechanisms. From this standpoint, the changes being introduced here will ensure equal opportunities and conditions for citizens to develop these areas and will help to address the most pressing issues in our country correctly, effectively, and promptly.

Article 48 of the Land Code, titled “Obligations of landowners, land users, and tenants using agricultural land”, should stipulate their obligation not to change the intended purpose of agricultural land use. This is because currently, there are instances of misuse of additional land allocated to dehkan farms, apart from the previously granted land with lifetime ownership rights. For example, these lands are being used for constructing houses, various buildings, barns, kitchens, and other structures.

Furthermore, we believe it necessary to supplement this article with obligations for dehkan farms and household plot owners such as “paying for land use, adhering to the procedure and deadlines for land tax payment, and covering the costs of restoring lands damaged by their fault”. This is because in practice, there are cases of non-compliance with the procedure and deadlines for land payments, and the responsibility for land degradation, especially economic responsibility, is very weak, including in dehkan farms and household plots. As a result, due to the lack of budget formation, particularly in the revenue part of local budgets, the most crucial socio-economic measures are not being financed locally.

Article 55 of the Land Code, titled "Provision of Land Plots to Citizens for Dehkan Farming," states: “Citizens with families who have resided in rural areas for at least three years are provided with a household plot for lifelong inheritable possession for dehkan farming, up to 0.35 hectares on irrigated lands and up to 0.5 hectares on non-irrigated (rainfed) lands, and up to 1 hectare on non-irrigated pastures in desert and arid zones. The requirement of three years' residence in rural areas does not apply to newly irrigated land plots. In this case, the size of the land plot provided for running a dehkan farm is determined considering the land plot previously provided or to be provided for lifelong inheritable possession for individual housing construction”. In our opinion, it is advisable to remove the word "Family" from this part. This is because today, it is of great socio-economic importance to allocate land plots for dehkan farming to all citizens who have the opportunity to create jobs in rural areas and increase production, regardless of their family status. Current practice shows that land plots are being allocated to vocational college graduates and other citizens for organizing dehkan farms. Additionally, this article stipulates that citizens living in rural areas who own livestock may be provided with land plots for temporary use for haymaking and grazing. The lack of a procedure for implementing this provision in practice is currently leading to increased degradation of these lands due to uncontrolled use of hayfields and pastures, a decrease in their value as means of production, and most importantly, disruption of their reproduction process.

Solution. In order to increase the efficiency of land use by dehkan and household farms, eliminate existing problems, and ensure the sustainable development of this sector, it is considered expedient to implement the following organizational, economic, legal, and technological measures.

First of all, it is necessary to improve the system of accounting for the lands of dehkan and household plots. In this regard, the introduction of modern geoinformation technologies, remote sensing, drones, and digital cadastral systems will ensure accurate accounting of land plots, reduce cases of misuse, and strengthen state and public oversight. The accuracy of land accounting is a key factor in ensuring the rational use of land resources.

Secondly, it is necessary to expand the mechanisms of financial support for dehqan and household farms. In particular, developing a clear organizational and economic mechanism for using land rights as collateral for bank loans, and introducing preferential mortgage and investment loans will serve to strengthen the material and technical base of these farms. This will expand the possibilities of implementing advanced agricultural technologies.

Thirdly, it is necessary to incentivize the application of advanced agricultural technologies in dehqan and household farms. By introducing greenhouses, drip irrigation, intensive horticulture, and water-saving technologies, it is possible to preserve and increase soil fertility, and improve the volume and quality of products. In this regard, it is advisable to expand state subsidies and technical advisory services.

Fourthly, the development of information and educational services for dehqan and household farms is of great importance. By increasing the use of Internet platforms, electronic consulting centers, and digital services, it is possible to provide landowners with timely information on agricultural technologies, market conditions, and legal issues. This will improve the management practices of dehqan and household farms.

Fifthly, it is necessary to eliminate legal gaps in land use by improving legislation. Amending certain articles of the Land Code in accordance with modern market relations, enforcing the targeted use of land, payment of land tax, and strengthening economic responsibility for the restoration of disturbed lands will contribute to the effective use of land resources.

Finally, it is necessary to develop a network of services at the district and local levels for delivering products from dehqan and household plots to markets. By expanding the logistics, storage, processing, and sales infrastructure, it is possible to increase the income of these farms and ensure their economic stability.

The consistent implementation of these proposals and solutions will serve to increase the efficiency of land use by dehqan and household farms, protect land resources, and ensure the sustainable development of agriculture.

Conclusion. The research results demonstrated that increasing the efficiency of land use by dehqan farms and household plots is crucial for the country's food security and sustainable agricultural development. Analysis confirmed that the main problems in this area are the low accuracy of land accounting, insufficient implementation of advanced agricultural technologies, and limited access to financial and information resources. In this regard, the necessity of introducing modern geoinformation technologies, improving financial support mechanisms, adapting legal norms to market relations, and developing service and information services was substantiated. The consistent implementation of these measures will ensure the rational use of lands by dehqan farms and household plots, and will serve to increase the efficiency of agricultural production.

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